

STUDIES IN DEHYDROGENATION. PART VII.

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The syntheses and selenium dehydrogenation of tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spirocyclohexane, 7-methyl- and 7-ethyl-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spirocyclohexane have been described.

The results obtained by the selenium dehydrogenation of tetrahydronaphthalene-spiro-cyclopentane derivatives had been described in a former communication in this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 350). The author's view explaining the ring transformation that takes place during dehydrogenation had also been advanced there. In the present communication the effect of selenium dehydrogenation on three tetrahydronaphthalene-spiro-cyclohexanes has been studied. The spiro-cyclohexanes synthesised for this purpose are 1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclohexane (I, R=H), 7-methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclohexane (I, R=Me) and 7-ethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclohexane (I, R=Et). All the three spiro-cyclohexanes are found to undergo ring transformation, exactly as in the case of the spiro-cyclopentane compounds (*loc. cit.*) during dehydrogenation with selenium with the formation of fully aromatic hydrocarbons. In all the cases studied here, it is found that along with ring transformation there occurs a loss of one carbon atom during dehydrogenation.

1 : 2 : 3 : 4-Tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclohexane (I, R=H) gives on dehydrogenation only phenanthrene and no anthracene or methylphenanthrene could be isolated from the dehydrogenation product. By an identical ring transformation and loss of one carbon atom, the spiro-cyclohexanes (I, R=Me) and (I, R=Et) afford 3-methylphenanthrene (II, R=Me) and 3-ethylphenanthrene (II, R=Et) respectively and no anthracene derivative could be detected in the dehydrogenation products.

This result is rather difficult to explain. From analogy with the cyclopentane series discussed in a previous paper (*loc. cit.*), the spiro-cyclohexane ring should be expected to furnish by similar fission and recyclisation a methylphenanthrene and a methylanthracene. It is quite

probable, however, that the cyclohexane ring undergoes partial dehydrogenation, fission then takes place with the formation of an intermediate product which by cyclisation and dehydrogenation furnishes phenanthrene according to the following scheme

In the absence of a better explanation this view has been adopted by the author as providing a satisfactory explanation of the curious behaviour of the *cyclohexane-spiro* compounds on dehydrogenation.

The spiro-hydrocarbon (I, R=H) has been synthesised in the following manner. The anhydride of *cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* is condensed with benzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, with the formation of a keto-acid which might be either (III, R=H) or (IV, R=H). The same keto-acid is also obtained by the condensation of the acid chloride of methyl *cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetate* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2015) with benzene in presence of aluminium chloride. Reduction of this keto-acid by the Clemmensen method gives an acid which has been proved to be *α-cyclohexane-γ-phenyl butyric acid* (V, R=H), on the ground that the ethyl ester of this acid does not condense with ethyl oxalate in presence of potassium ethoxide. This acid (V, R=H) on cyclisation with 85% sulphuric acid gives the spiro-ketone (VI, R=H), which on reduction with amalgamated zinc and hydrochloric acid gives the spiro-hydrocarbon (I, R=H).

By an extension of this process the spiro-hydrocarbons (I, R=Me and R=Et) have also been synthesised. The anhydride of *cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* is condensed with toluene and ethylbenzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride giving the keto-acids (III, R=Me) and (III, R=Et) respectively. These keto-acids on reduction by the Clemmensen method give *α-cyclohexane-γ-(β-tolyl)-butyric acid* (V, R=Me) and *α-cyclohexane-γ-(p-tolyl) phenyl butyric acid* (V, R=Et) respectively. The position of the *cyclohexane* ring in the two *γ-arylbutyric acids* has been proved from the observation that the ethyl esters of these two acids do not condense with ethyl oxalate in presence of potassium ethoxide. These two *γ-arylbutyric acids* on cyclisation with 85% sulphuric acid give the two spiro-ketones (VI, R=Me) and (VI, R=Et). On reduction by the Clemmensen method these spiro-ketones give 7-methyl-1, 2:3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-*cyclohexane* (I, R=Me) and 7-ethyl-1, 2:3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-*cyclohexane* (I, R=Et).

EXPERIMENTAL.

α-cycloHexane-β-benzoylpropionic Acid (III, R=H).—(a) Aluminium chloride (25 g.) was slowly added to an ice-cooled solution of the anhydride of *cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* (34 g.) in dry benzene (100 c.c.). The mixture was allowed to stand at the room temperature for 12 hours after which it was heated at 60-65° for 3 hours and decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. Excess of benzene was removed in steam and the thick oily product was dissolved in dilute sodium carbonate solution, filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid when the keto-acid separated as a thick oil which slowly became semi-solid. The mass was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid from which the keto-acid slowly crystallised in colourless plates. On recrystallisation

it had m. p. 117-18°, yield 12 g. (Found: C, 73.2; H, 7.4. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 73.2; H, 7.3 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in methyl alcoholic solution, crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 132-33°. (Found: C, 63.2; H, 7.0. $C_{14}H_{21}O_2N_2$ requires C, 63.4; H, 6.9 per cent).

(b) The acid chloride prepared from 20 g. methyl *cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetate* was mixed with dry benzene (50 c.c.) cooled in ice and aluminium chloride (26 g.) was added to it. The mixture was allowed to stand at the room temperature for 12 hours and was then treated with ice. Excess of benzene was distilled in steam, the residual oil was extracted with ether, washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution, dried with sodium sulphate and ether removed. The keto-ester (8.1 g.) distilled at 165-70°/3 mm. as a thick oil, which readily solidified on cooling. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) as white needles, m.p. 65-66°. (Found: C, 73.5; H, 7.9. $C_{18}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 73.8; H, 7.7 per cent). It was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash and the resulting keto-acid was crystallised from acetic acid as plates, m.p. 117-18°.

α-cyclohexane-γ-phenylbutyric Acid (V, R=H).—*α-Cyclohexane-β-benzoyl-propionic acid* (8 g.), amalgamated zinc (50 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) were boiled for 24 hours. The reduced product was extracted with ether, ether removed and the residue was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution. The filtered solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the separated solid acid collected, dried and crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in flakes, m.p. 93°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 77.4; H, 8.6. $C_{14}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 77.6; H, 8.6 per cent).

The *amide* was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 130-31°. (Found: C, 82.2; H, 8.1. $C_{21}H_{28}ON$ requires C, 82.1; H, 8.1 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared by the action of ethyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride. It is a thin colourless oil, b.p. 111-12°/5 mm. (Found: C, 78.3; H, 9.3. $C_{17}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.5; H, 9.2 per cent).

1-Keto-1: 2: 3: 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2: 2-spiro-cyclohexane (VI, R=H).—*α-cyclohexane-γ-phenylbutyric acid* (6.5 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (19.5 c.c.) and water (6.5 c.c.) were heated on a steam-bath for 1½ hours with stirring. The mixture was poured into ice, extracted with ether; the ether extract washed with dilute ammonia and water, dried with sodium sulphate and distilled. It is a colourless oil possessing a characteristic odour, b.p. 145°/3 mm., yield 3.7 g., d_4^{20} , 1.07224; n_D^{20} , 1.56435; $[R_L]_D = 64.9$. (Found: C, 83.9; H, 8.5. $C_{14}H_{18}O$ requires C, 84.1; H, 8.4 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 187-188°. (Found: C, 70.7; H, 7.9. $C_{16}H_{21}ON_2$ requires C, 70.8; H, 7.7 per cent).

1: 2: 3: 4-Tetrahydronaphthalene-2: 2-spiro-cyclohexane (I, R=H).—The foregoing spiro-ketone (3.7 g.) was boiled with hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) and amalgamated zinc (20 g.) for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, the ether extract washed, dried and distilled. It is a colourless liquid, b.p. 115-17°/3 mm., yield 2.5 g., d_4^{20} , 0.98886; n_D^{20} , 1.54314, $[R_L]_D = 63.76$ (Calc., 63.47). (Found: C, 89.8; H, 10.3. $C_{12}H_{16}$ requires C, 90.0; H, 10.0 per cent).

Selenium dehydrogenation of the spiro hydrocarbon (I, R=H).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2.3 g.) was heated with powdered selenium in a metal-bath at 280-300° for 6 hours and at 340-50° for 24 hours. The product was thoroughly extracted with ether, solvent distilled off and the residual oil was distilled over sodium under reduced pressure. The liquid distillate was warmed with picric acid in alcoholic solution and the separated picrate after two crystallisations from alcohol was obtained as yellow needles, m.p. 144° and the mixed m.p. with the picrate of an

authentic sample of phenanthrene was 144°. The hydrocarbon, regenerated from this picrate by distribution between dilute ammonium hydroxide and ether, crystallised from alcohol in flakes m.p. 99°. The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of phenanthrene was not depressed. (Found : C, 94.4; H, 5.6. $C_{14}H_{10}$ requires C, 94.5; H, 5.5 per cent).

α-cyclohexane-β-(p-toluoxy) propionic Acid (III, R=Me).—(a) It was prepared from toluene (70 c.c.), anhydride of *cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* (25 g.) and aluminium chloride (40 g.), according to the method followed in the preparation of *α-cyclohexane-β-benzoylpropionic acid*. It was crystallised from petrol (b.p. 90-100°) as colourless long prisms, m.p. 129-30°, yield 27 g. (Found : C, 73.8; H, 7.7. $C_{14}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.8; H, 7.7 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in flakes, m.p. 166°. (Found : C, 64.2; H, 7.3. $C_{11}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires C, 64.3; H, 7.3 per cent).

(b) The acid chloride prepared from 15 g. of methyl *cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetate* and dry toluene (50 c.c.) was treated with aluminium chloride (20g.). The product, a keto-ester, was worked in the usual manner and distilled as a pale yellow liquid at 180-82°/5 mm. It solidified on stirring with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-50°). It crystallised from petrol (b.p. 40-60°) in stout needles, m.p. 65-6°. (Found : C, 74.5; H, 8.1. $C_{17}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 74.4; H, 8.0 per cent). This keto ester on hydrolysis with alcoholic potash gave a keto acid, m.p. 129-30°, and the mixed m.p. with a sample prepared by method (a) remained unaltered.

α-cyclohexane-γ-p-tolyl-butyric Acid (V, R=Me).—The preceding keto-acid (22 g.) was gently boiled with amalgamated zinc (110 g.) and hydrochloric acid (110 c.c.) for 24 hours. The product was purified as in the case of the acid (V, R=H). It crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in needles, m.p. 99-100°, yield 14.5 g. (Found : C, 78.0; H, 8.7. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.1; H, 8.9 per cent).

The *p-toluidide* crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 128-129°. (Found : C, 82.5; H, 8.8. $C_{20}H_{26}ON$ requires C, 82.4; H, 8.7 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared by the action of ethyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride. It is a thin colourless oil, b.p. 115-16°/6 mm. (Found : C, 78.7; H, 9.6. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.9; H, 9.5 per cent).

1-Keto-7-methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclohexane (VI, R=Me).—*α-cyclohexane-γ-(p-tolyl) butyric acid* (10 g.) was cyclised by heating with concentrated sulphuric acid (30 c.c.) and water (10 c.c.) at 100°. It is a colourless oil, b.p. 158-60°/4 mm, yield 6.8 g. (Found : C, 84.1; H, 8.9. $C_{18}H_{22}O$ requires C, 84.2; H, 8.8 per cent).

The *oxime* was prepared by heating the spiro-keto compound with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine solution. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 139-40°. (Found : C, 79.2; H, 8.6. $C_{18}H_{21}ON$ requires C, 79.0; H, 8.6 per cent).

7-Methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclohexane (I, R=Me).—The foregoing spiro-ketone (5.6 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (30 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) for 18 hours. It is a thin oil, b.p. 155-156°/8mm, yield 4.4 g. (Found : C, 89.4; H, 10.4. $C_{18}H_{22}$ requires C, 89.7; H, 10.3 per cent).

Selenium Dehydrogenation of 7-Methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclohexane.—3.5G. of the spiro-hydrocarbon was heated with selenium (6g.) in a metal-bath at 280-300° for 8 hours and at 340-355° for 30 hours. The product was extracted with ether and distilled over sodium under reduced pressure when 1.2 g. of a yellow liquid distillate was obtained. This was treated with alcoholic solution of picric acid and on crystallisation from alcohol the

picrate was obtained as bright yellow needles, m.p. 133-34°. The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the picrate by distribution between ammonium hydroxide and ether. The ether solution on evaporation gave the solid hydrocarbon, which on crystallisation from methyl alcohol melted at 62°. The picrate, prepared from this hydrocarbon crystallised from alcohol in bright yellow needles, m.p. 137-138°. The mixed m.p. of this hydrocarbon with a sample of 3-methylphenanthrene, prepared by Haworth's method, was 62°. The mixed m.p. of its picrate with that of 3-methylphenanthrene showed no depression of m.p.

α-cyclohexane-β-(p-ethyl)-benzoyl propionic Acid (III, R=Et).—(a) It was prepared from the anhydride of cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (16.8 g.), ethylbenzene (12 g.), aluminium chloride (26 g.), in carbon disulphide solution (75 c.c.) according to the procedure followed in the case of *α-cyclohexane-β-(p-toluyloyl) propionic acid*. It was crystallised from petrol (b.p. 70-80°) in beautiful flakes, m.p. 117-18°, yield 17.5 g. (Found: C, 74.2; H, 8.1. $C_{17}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 74.4; H, 8.0 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 144°. (Found: C, 65.3; H, 7.6. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires C, 65.3; H, 7.5 per cent).

(b) The acid chloride prepared from 20 g. of methyl cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetate and 12 g. of ethylbenzene in 75 c.c. carbon disulphide were treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (26 g.) in cold. The product, a keto-ester, was worked in the usual manner and was distilled as a thick oil at 202-203°/7 mm, yield 15.5 g. (Found: C, 74.8; H, 8.3. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 8.3 per cent). The keto ester was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash and the keto-acid, so obtained, was crystallised from petrol (b.p. 70-80°) and had m.p. and mixed m.p. with a sample of the keto-acid prepared by method (a), 117-18°.

α-cyclohexane-γ-(p-ethyl)-phenylbutyric Acid (V, R=Et).—The foregoing keto-acid (18.5 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (100 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.) for 24 hours. The reduced acid was purified by extraction with sodium carbonate and then by distillation at 220-25°/9 mm. The solid distillate was crystallised from petrol (b.p. 70-80°) in prisms, m.p. 67-68°, yield 13.2 g. (Found: C, 78.5; H, 9.2. $C_{17}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.5; H, 9.2 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared by the action of ethyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride. It is a thin colourless oil, b.p. 104-105°/6 mm, yield 12.8 g. (Found: C, 79.0; H, 9.7. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 79.1; H, 9.7 per cent).

1-Keto-7-ethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclohexane (VI, R=Et).—*α-cyclohexane-γ-(p-ethyl) phenylbutyric acid* (11 g.) was cyclised with concentrated sulphuric acid (33 c.c.) and water (11 c.c.) at 100°. The product was a thick colourless liquid, b.p. 195-97°/9 mm, yield 7.5 g. d_4^{25} , 1.0450, n_D^{25} , 1.5536, $[R_L]_D^{25}$ = 74.0 (Calc., 72.7). (Found: C, 84.0; H, 9.2. $C_{17}H_{22}O$ requires C, 84.3; H, 9.2 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 203-204°. (Found: C, 72.3; H, 8.5. $C_{18}H_{22}ON_2$ requires C, 72.2; H, 8.4 per cent).

7-Ethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclohexane (I, R=Et).—The foregoing spiro ketone (6 g.) was reduced by the Clemmensen method with amalgamated zinc (30 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.). The product was purified by distillation over sodium and was a colourless liquid, b.p. 168-69°/8 mm, yield 4.8 g. d_4^{25} , 0.972787, n_D^{25} , 1.538808, $[R_L]_D^{25}$ = 73.4, (Calc., 72.7). (Found: C, 89.3; H, 10.4. $C_{17}H_{24}$ requires C, 89.5; H, 10.5 per cent).

Selenium Dehydrogenation of 7-Ethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclohexane.—The spiro-hydrocarbon (3 g.) was heated with selenium (4 g.) in a metal-bath at 300-320° for 6 hours and at 340-350° for 24 hours. The product was thoroughly extracted with ether and distilled over sodium. A liquid distillate (0.9 g.) at 165-175°/5 mm. was obtained. It was treated with picric acid in alcoholic solution and the separated picrate after crystallisation from alcohol was obtained as orange needles, m.p. 117-18°. The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of picrate of 3-ethylpenanthrene, prepared from 3-phenanthroyl methyl ketone (Haworth and Mavin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1012), was 117-18°. (Found: C, 60.7; H, 4.0. $C_{12}H_{12}O_7N_3$ requires C, 60.7; H, 3.9 per cent). The picrate was decomposed with ammonia and the regenerated hydrocarbon after distillation over sodium was obtained as colourless oil, which did not solidify. (Found: C, 93.0; H, 6.8. $C_{14}H_{14}$ requires C, 93.2; H, 6.8 per cent).

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